

**The Economic Impact of the COVID-19 Induced Redistribution of Resources
away from Cancer Services in England: A Statistical Analysis and OLG Model
Approach to Inform Policy**

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Abstract

This dissertation implements a three-pronged approach to explore the economic impact of the COVID-19 pandemic-induced redistribution of resources away from cancer services in England. Firstly, a review of current medical research and statistical techniques is conducted to identify the cause of the reduction in cancer diagnoses during the pandemic, to understand how the outlook of crucial NHS cancer pathways have been affected over the next 5 years, and to investigate distributional changes in cancer stage diagnoses in England. The newfound role of telemedicine and the impact of cancer on employment prospects are also investigated for policy-making purposes. Secondly, this dissertation constructs an Overlapping Generations (OLG) model involving cancer to investigate potential adverse future macroeconomic effects. This research is utilised to propose policies to optimally mitigate these undesirable economic impacts. Finally, research generalisability to other chronic diseases and healthcare systems is discussed.

Chapter 1 - Introduction

By April 2020 in England, all National Health Service (NHS) hospitals ceased non-urgent operations (Iacobucci, 2020). Much of the surgical community was redirected into areas far from their specialities (Weilongorska and Ekwobi, 2020) with operating theatres transformed into COVID-19 critical care wards (Kursumovic et al., 2021). As a result, cancer services in this country were chronically neglected, with diagnosis and treatment services experiencing significant delays (Sud et al., 2020).

Cancer outcomes are negatively associated with delays in time to diagnosis and treatment (Neal et al., 2015). Cancer not only causes over 1 in 4 deaths in the UK (Baker, 2021), but cancer services cost the NHS £5 billion a year (GOV.UK, 2016). This figure is eclipsed by the annual £19 billion cost of cancer to society, predominantly due to associated productivity losses (GOV.UK, 2016). Thus, the ramifications of such an interruption could have potentially shattering economic effects in the foreseeable future. This is of particular concern in the context of a healthcare system that has experienced a decade of inadequate funding that has not aligned with growing healthcare demands and an economy which encountered the largest pandemic-induced GDP reduction of all G7 countries (British Medical Association, 2023). This project's aim is to investigate the economic impact of this interruption and to provide a timely set of policy recommendations to mitigate this impact.

This dissertation employs a three-pronged approach to achieve the research task. The first prong involves statistical techniques, such as linear regression, Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) models and visual statistics, to determine the cause of the decline in cancer diagnoses during the pandemic, to forecast the outlook of NHS cancer pathways (the journey a cancer patient goes from initial symptoms to treatment) over the next 5 years based on current trends, and to investigate distributional changes of the stages at which cancers are diagnosed in England, respectively. Moreover, recent medical literature is reviewed to enhance the understanding of how the interruption of the pandemic, has affected, and may continue to affect, various cancer-related variables. The second prong constructs an OLG model involving cancer and attempts to model the aforementioned effects as exogenous shocks in order to investigate potential negative future macroeconomic effects. The third prong combines

this OLG model, alongside the earlier findings, to develop strategies to best mitigate the adverse economic impacts of the pandemic-induced disruption to cancer services.

Chapter 2 - Literature Review

The literature reviewed is divided into three subtopics: Impact of COVID-19 on Cancer Diagnosis and Treatment Pathways; The Role of Telemedicine; and Impact of Cancer on Employment.

2.1. Impact of COVID-19 on Cancer Diagnosis and Treatment Pathways

The pandemic led to significant reductions in diagnoses of various cancer types, including breast cancer (Gathani, Dodwell and Horgan, 2022), lung cancer (Maxwell and Weller, 2022) and prostate cancer (Leszczynski et al., 2022), the three most common cancers in England (CRUK, 2015a). In England, patients typically present symptomatically to GPs (Hamilton, 2010), for example, 70% of lung cancers are diagnosed via primary care (Maxwell and Weller, 2022). This percentage was likely amplified during the pandemic in the absence of screening programmes as a route to diagnosis (Maxwell and Weller, 2022). However, fear of contracting COVID-19 in public spaces may have contributed to shifts in demand for healthcare (Zhang, 2021) with fear of contracting the virus and burdening healthcare services potentially leading to individuals becoming reluctant to visit GPs and foregoing medical care (Rutter et al., 2020). This dissertation implements statistical techniques to explore whether the reduction in cancer diagnoses during the pandemic was caused by avoided GP visits, thereby helping to inform policy later in the dissertation.

Higher practice of the NHS' 2-week-wait pathway (2WW, an NHS target for urgent referrals to be investigated by a specialist within two weeks) is positively associated with reduced mortality and late-stage cancer diagnoses (Round et al., 2021). Cancer patients registered with GPs with the lowest use of urgent referrals are reported to experience excess mortality of 7% (Møller et al., 2015), highlighting the importance of 2WW in reducing excess mortality and late-stage diagnoses. During the pandemic, there was a 20.2% decline in patients urgently referred from primary care (predominantly GPs) (Watt, Sullivan and Aggarwal, 2022). Furthermore, delays regarding the NHS' guideline for cancer treatment initiation within 62 days of an urgent referral from primary care are associated with poorer outcomes (Watt, Sullivan and Aggarwal, 2022). Research shows that treatment delays of 2-6 months can lead to

progression of early-stage tumours from curable to terminal (Sud et al., 2020). In the 3-year NHS England plan to tackle the backlog of cancer cases, local systems were asked to return the number of patients waiting more than 62 days from urgent referral to treatment to pre-pandemic levels (Reframe, 2023). This dissertation contributes to existing literature by implementing statistical techniques to gain insight into how the pandemic has affected the outlooks of crucial NHS cancer pathways and to assess the widely reported claim that later-stage diagnoses are expected to increase.

2.2. The Role of Telemedicine

Telemedicine has had a multifaceted impact on the UK's cancer pathway: the number of general medicine consultations conducted 'virtually' increased from 10% pre-pandemic to 75% at its peak (McCall, 2020). Furthermore, 95% of Cancer Research UK's (CRUK) trials were halted during the pandemic (Research Professional News, 2020), and many global trials were halted or postponed (Sessa et al., 2022). Thus, cancer trials were forced to adopt new virtual approaches, with many switching patients to virtual visits during trials (Sessa et al., 2022).

Telemedicine promises to have lasting impacts in the fields of general medicine (McCall, 2020) and cancer trials (Sessa et al., 2022), both key components in enhancing cancer survival outcomes. The NHS announced a long-term plan to increase telemedicine and reduce face-to-face appointments by up to a third by 2024 to help free up hospital capacity (Barrie, 2023), aligning with a growing expectation that telemedicine can be the answer to the NHS' cancer backlog (McCall, 2020).

During the pandemic, reduction in 2WW urgent referrals was greater for those residing in poorer areas (Watt, Sullivan and Aggarwal, 2022). Moreover, minorities were underrepresented in all COVID-19 clinical trials where race and ethnicity were reported (Sessa et al., 2022). By reducing geographical burdens, telemedicine can reduce these inequalities (Sessa et al., 2022). Telemedicine can accelerate clinical trial accessibility and accruals (Sessa et al., 2022), with one widespread US study finding an almost 1:1 relationship between cancer clinical trial participation and cancer survival outcomes correlation (Unger et al., 2016). However, telemedicine can also widen treatment inequalities with regards to age. The elderly was largely "telemedicine unready" during

the pandemic due to factors including hearing problems, dementia and lack of equipment (West, Barzi and Wong, 2022) and were therefore the group most likely to defer treatment (Zhang, 2021). This dissertation contributes to existing literature by offering timely strategies to ensure effective and equitable utilisation of telemedicine in the NHS cancer pathway. By employing the OLG model, this dissertation examines the potential for telemedicine, if implemented according to these proposed strategies, to counteract the unfavourable economic consequences resulting from the reduction of cancer treatment productivity during the pandemic.

2.3. Impact of Cancer on Employment

With over one million working age cancer survivors estimated in the UK by 2030 (Maddams, Utley and Møller, 2012), the impact of cancer on employment is a key consideration for the proposed research task. Not only do the physical and psychological burdens of cancer reduce ability to work during treatment (Luker et al., 2013), but post-treatment employment trajectories are also adversely affected (Blinder and Gany, 2020). Whilst many survivors decide to reassess priorities and retire after surviving cancer, for many this reduction in full-time work is an undesirable side effect, inducing financial and psychological stress (Blinder and Gany, 2020). A UK study of cancer survivors found a significant full-time employment reduction of 53% pre-diagnosis to 33% post-diagnosis, with average weekly hours reducing from 38 hours to 32 hours. Furthermore, those individuals who discussed employment plans with their treatment team experienced significantly higher weekly return-to-work rates (36.7 versus 29.4 hours) (Luker et al., 2013). Early diagnosis was associated with increased ability to work during treatment (Luker et al., 2013). Recent literature has predicted a forthcoming wave of later-stage diagnoses in England (Sessa et al., 2022), which would result in less people being able to work during more taxing late-stage cancer treatments, such as chemotherapy (CRUK, 2020).

This dissertation contributes by modelling the economic impact of the estimated reduction in labour productivity using the OLG model, and guides policy to mitigate this negative effect by increasing return-to-work rates for cancer survivors in England, thereby aiding the economy in the future.

The overarching contribution of this dissertation is the unique combination of rigorous medical research, statistical analysis and economic theory to present a comprehensive and timely set of recommendations aimed at mitigating the adverse economic effects of the COVID-induced redistribution of resources away from cancer services in England. The dynamic economic model introduced represents a novel contribution to existing literature, having been specifically designed to capture the effects of cancer on this economy and to provide an intuitive and accessible framework to discuss the macroeconomic implications of changes in cancer services. This enhances the originality and potential applicability of this research.

Chapter 3 - Data & Methodology

3.1. Data

Data for Monthly New Cancer Diagnoses (section **4.1**) and Monthly New Diagnoses by Stage (section **4.3**) was sourced from the COVID-19 rapid cancer registration and treatment database. Rapid cancer registration was implemented during the pandemic to provide faster cancer reporting but consequently suffers from lower quality. However, this data can “be used to aid the planning of cancer services in recovering from COVID-19” (CancerData, 2023), thus it is applicable for our research thesis.

Data quality for these two variables is lower for more recent months, suffering from “slightly lower completeness from November 2022 onwards”. To strike a balance between ensuring data quality and guiding policy using the latest information, the scope of data analysis for these variables was limited up to September 2022. Both datasets were cleaned and processed in Microsoft Excel. For Monthly New Cancer Diagnoses, data was initially presented by age-group and so a summation over all age groups for each month was done to obtain a monthly ‘Total’ statistic. Furthermore, Stage at Diagnosis data was processed using Excel’s SUMIFS function to find total Monthly Diagnoses by Stage. A new variable called ‘Share of Total Diagnoses by Stage’ was created to investigate distributional changes in this variable over time.

Data concerning Monthly Attended GP Appointments (section **4.1**) was obtained from NHS Digital. While this dataset suffered from lower quality during the pandemic, the “low quality” data had been suppressed. Fortunately, the dataset investigated in this dissertation did not contain any suppressed data.

Data regarding Monthly 2WW performance (section **4.2**) and Monthly 62-day Treatment Initiation performance (section **4.2**) were sourced from the NHS England Cancer Waiting Times dataset. They required little processing as the raw forms were accessible. These datasets are generally considered high quality as they are “finalised in line with NHS England and NHS Improvement revisions policy” (NHS England, 2019).

3.2. Methods – Data Analysis

Section 4.1 applies visual analysis to Monthly New Cancer Diagnoses and Monthly Attended GP Appointments from December 2019 to September 2022. The ‘Date’ column was removed from both datasets and a regression fitted to investigate the association between these two variables:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{NewCancerDiagnoses}_i &= \text{intercept} + \beta * \text{AttendedGPAppointments}_i, \\ i &= 1, \dots, 32, \end{aligned}$$

where i represents different months between December 2019 and September 2022. The relationship between these two variables appears linear and exhibits homoscedasticity in Figure 3 - a linear model is suitable here. Whilst this analysis provides a quick and intuitive investigation into the association between these variables, this study might fail to include other important predictors of Monthly New Cancer Diagnoses and potential confounders.

In section 4.2, ARIMA models are applied to forecast crucial NHS cancer pathways using R’s *auto.arima* function. ARIMA models were chosen due to their simplicity and comparable performance with other time series models on routinely collected healthcare data (Earnest et al., 2019). The *accuracy* function in R demonstrated good fit for all three ARIMA models, indicated by low error (such as mean squared error) and low autocorrelation between residuals when evaluated on training data. One limitation of ARIMA models is that forecasted values are functions of past values. Thus, if data quality was compromised in COVID-impacted months, the accuracy of future forecasts may suffer.

In section 4.3, the methodology employed visual statistics to examine whether the pandemic caused increased later-stage cancer diagnoses. Monthly Total New Cancer Diagnoses by Stage from January 2018 to September 2022 was plotted. This approach provided little indication of distributional changes, so a new variable, the number of diagnoses by stage as a proportion of total diagnoses, was created and plotted over the same period, enabling discussion on distributional changes. A limitation of this study

was the presence of ‘unknown’ cases hindering definitive conclusions from being drawn. Additionally, cancers often take a considerable amount of time to metastasize (spread to distant organs and becomes ‘late-stage’), and the time horizon studied might not have allowed enough time to account for this effect.

3.3. Methods – OLG Model

To address the economic impact of the pandemic-induced shock to cancer services, this dissertation constructs a dynamic economic model which can describe changes in variables over time. Specifically, a two-period OLG model is constructed, incorporating various ‘cancer-related’ variables to introduce the shock into the model.

Simplifying assumptions are made in this model which limit scope and applicability. Firstly, healthcare is assumed to be fully publicly provided. This assumption is not unreasonable in the given context – all UK residents have access to public healthcare but only 10% have private medical insurance (Statista, 2019), but may limit generalisability to other settings where private healthcare is prevalent. The model assumes health status is not inherited from parents. In the cancer context, this assumption is again not far-fetched, with only 3% of cancers estimated to be caused by an inherited faulty gene (NHS, 2018). What is more likely to violate this assumption is lifestyle habits passed down from parents to offspring. The model assumes the NHS is funded through taxed income. This assumption is sound, given income tax is the NHS’ largest source of income (Aldred, 2023). Furthermore, the model assumes that young agents have perfect information regarding their survival probability, φ_t , when deciding how much to consume and save. In reality this assumption is likely violated, as accurately quantifying such probabilities is challenging.

The model fails to account for the ability of intergenerational lifestyle changes to alter cancer incidence. For example, around 45% of the UK population smoked in 1974, whereas this is less than 15% today (GOV.UK, 2013), with smoking being the biggest preventable cause of cancer (CRUK, 2019). Furthermore, the model does not account for varying incidence rates in different demographics such as black women being 41% more likely to die of breast cancer than white women (Giaquinto et al., 2022). These

two factors expose the model's ineffectiveness in informing policies targeting different demographics / generations with personalised and effective cancer treatment.

Despite its limitations, the proposed OLG model's focus on the dynamic interplay between the performance of cancer services and the wider economy in England provides insights into the long-term economic effects of the pandemic-induced shock and provides a concise framework to inform policies to mitigate these adverse economic effects. This study acknowledges the model's limitations and further research is necessary to incorporate more realistic assumptions for a more comprehensive analysis of this research question.

Chapter 4 – Effects of COVID-19 on Cancer in England

4.1. How did COVID-19 affect Cancer Diagnoses?

One major impact of the pandemic was the postponement of cancer screening, a crucial technique in detecting early-stage cancers in this country, which resulted in around 200,000 people per week in the UK missing out on screening procedures (CRUK - Science blog, 2020). This represents a missed opportunity to detect early-stage cancers. This delay in screening is likely to lead to more advanced-stage diagnoses in the future (Sessa et al., 2022), which typically carry worse prognoses (McPhail et al., 2015).

In England, cancer patients typically present symptomatically to GPs (Hamilton, 2010). Figure 1 depicts the sharp reduction in cancer diagnoses that occurred during the pandemic. It is unlikely that this reduction was caused by a sudden decline in true cancer rates in England, and more likely attributed to a decrease in individuals seeking medical attention due to fear and anxiety of contracting the virus or burdening the NHS (Richards et al., 2020).

This dissertation utilised two time series datasets encompassing the period from December 2019 to September 2022 to investigate the potential cause of this phenomenon. The first time series concerning Monthly New Cancer Diagnoses in England for all cancer types is depicted in Figure 1 and the second time series concerning Monthly Number of Attended GP Appointments in England is depicted in Figure 2. The blue vertical dotted line in all plots represents the month the first lockdown was introduced – March 2020. The trend observed in Figure 1 appears similar to that of Figure 2 and consequently, linear regression analysis was used to investigate the relationship between these two variables, with Monthly New Cancer Diagnoses as the dependent variable and Monthly Number of Attended GP Appointments as the independent variable.

The results revealed a statistically significant positive linear relationship between these two variables. Figure 3 illustrates this strong positive association as well as the fitted regression line. The results of this regression are presented in Figure 4. The very small p-value on the independent variable indicates that the number of GP appointments

attended during the pandemic significantly influenced number of diagnoses in the same period. The high R^2 value suggests the variation in the Monthly New Cancer Diagnoses is well explained by the variation in Monthly Number of Attended GP Appointments during the investigated period. These findings converge to the conclusion that the reduction in cancer diagnoses during the pandemic was partly attributable to the decrease in GP visits.

Overall, a deferral of the NHS screening programmes will inevitably result in more severe advanced-stage cancers in the population. Similarly, the regression analysis indicates that the reluctance caused by fear and anxiety to attend healthcare settings during the pandemic will have resulted in cancer cases remaining undiagnosed. This will lead to cancer progression in individuals whose cancers could have been identified through screening programmes, or a GP visit, in the absence of the pandemic. These factors will result in delayed diagnoses and poorer prognoses for affected patients (Watt, Sullivan and Aggarwal, 2022).

Figure 1 - Monthly New Cancer Diagnoses in England (All Types, Dec 2019 - Sep 2022)

Figure 2 - Monthly Number of Attended GP Appointments in England (Dec 2019 - Sep 2022)

Figure 3 - Graph showing observed values and fitted regression line for Number of attended GP Appointments and Number of new Cancer (all types) diagnoses during different months of the Covid pandemic in England (Dec 2019 - Sep 2022)

Figure 4 - Linear Regression Model Summary

		<i>Dependent variable:</i>
		`Number of New Cancer Diagnoses in England (All Types)`
`Number of Attended GP Appointments in England`		0.001*** (0.0001)
Constant		9,495.048*** (2,499.845)
Observations		34
R ²		0.542
Adjusted R ²		0.528
Residual Std. Error		1,926.185 (df = 32)
F Statistic		37.873*** (df = 1; 32)

Note: * p<0.1; ** p<0.05; *** p<0.01

4.2. How did COVID-19 affect Cancer Pathways in England?

Time to diagnosis from initial symptoms (TTD) and time to treatment initiation (TTI) are key nodes of the cancer pathway. Reducing them offers improved prognoses and outcomes for patients (Sud et al., 2020, Cone et al., 2020). In England, the ‘2 Week Wait Urgent Referral’ (2WW) pathway was introduced to mitigate diagnostic delays and minimise TTD, aiming for cases to be seen by a specialist within two weeks following an urgent referral from primary care (Round et al., 2021). Higher practice of 2WW is associated with reduced mortality and fewer late-stage diagnoses (Round et al., 2021). A study found that a cancer patient registered to a GP with the lowest utilisation of urgent referral had excess mortality of 7% (95% CI of 5% to 8%), highlighting the efficacy of the pathway in England (Møller et al., 2015).

In 2016, almost 40% of cancer cases in England were diagnosed via 2WW (CRUK, 2018). It is therefore paramount to investigate the impact of COVID-19 on this pathway. To this end, monthly data up to December 2022 regarding the percentage of patients seen by a specialist within two weeks of an urgent referral from primary care was collected. The NHS sets a standard for 93% of patients to be evaluated by a specialist within two weeks of an urgent referral (Cancer Alliance UK, 2023). Meeting or exceeding this target is desirable given the benefits of the pathway.

ARIMA models were employed to examine how COVID-19 has affected this pathway and were fit to two distinct sets of monthly data pertaining the proportion of patients successfully seen via 2WW. The first dataset spanned from October 2009 to February 2020, excluding data from the COVID-impacted period. The second incorporated data from both the pre-COVID period (October 2009 to February 2020) and the most recent data from the COVID and post-COVID era (March 2020 to December 2022). This research first forecasted 2WW expected performance until December 2027 in the absence of COVID and compared this with a second forecast which incorporated both the observed data from the COVID and post-COVID period and also projected until this date. The goal was to simulate how the pandemic has altered the outlook of this pathway.

The forecasts are shown in Figures 5 and 6:

Figure 5 - 80% confidence Auto-ARIMA Forecasts for 2WW pathway, Apr 2020 - Dec 2027 monthly, not including data from COVID period

Figure 6 - 80% confidence Auto-ARIMA Forecasts for 2WW pathway, Jan 2023 - Dec 2027 monthly, including data from COVID period

The black line in these figures represents observed values and the red line represents forecasted values with an 80% confidence band included. Figure 5 shows that even before the pandemic, the percentage of people seen via the 2WW within two weeks was beginning to wane but was still close to the 93% target, with the ARIMA forecast until December 2027 predicting a clear downward trend. Figure 6 shows how the pandemic exacerbated this problem – there was a drastic reduction in the number of people seen via 2WW when the pandemic began and consequently, the pandemic has worsened the forecast of 2WW until 2027.

The TTI node is next analysed and more specifically the 62-day pathway - a national guideline which aims to have patients wait no longer than 62 days from a primary care urgent referral to treatment initiation (CRUK, 2022). As primary care is “the most crucial interface for diagnosis and referral to hospital-based care” (Watt, Sullivan and Aggarwal, 2022), widespread adherence to this guideline can lead to significantly better national outcomes. Delays regarding treatment initiation can lead to cancer progression,

later-stage diagnoses and poorer outcomes for patients from a tumour being curable (at near-normal life expectancy) to incurable (with very reduced life expectancy) (Sud et al., 2020). The NHS has established an 85% standard for this pathway (Cancer Alliance UK, 2023). The latest data was analysed and an ARIMA model was fitted to forecast the future of this pathway:

Figure 7 presents a situation akin to Figure 6. Even before the COVID-impacted era, the percentage of people successfully treated via this pathway was already decreasing, and the pandemic has only exacerbated this pre-existing problem. This might be attributed to a decade of NHS underfunding which has failed to match growing demand (British Medical Association, 2023). In February 2022, NHS England published a 3-year delivery plan whereby local systems were asked to return the number of patients waiting more than 62 days for TTI to pre-pandemic levels by March 2023 (British Medical Association, 2023). The latest data in Figure 7, obtained in January 2023,

indicates a value of 54%. This analysis suggests it is highly improbable pre-pandemic levels will be achieved within two months. Rather, the ARIMA forecast paints a bleak picture and exposes the NHS' considerable failure to meet their operational standard and 3-year post-COVID recovery plan.

As ARIMA models do not account for external factors, for example future NHS funding increases/cuts, one may consider the applicability of ARIMA models in the context of an unprecedented shock to the healthcare system. However, these models are useful in identifying trends, providing insight into how the pandemic has affected the NHS' crucial cancer pathways and highlighting the need for targeted policymaker intervention to deviate from these worrying trends and to alleviate these grave projections.

A mathematical model revealed that a 2–6-month delay to treatment leads to a “substantial proportion of patients with early-stage tumours progressing from having curable to incurable disease” (Sud et al., 2020). Furthermore, the study estimates that a 2-month delay in a 2WW referral costs up to 0.7 life-years per patient, a measure which accounts for the reduction in the quality of life because of disease burden. These findings underscore the need for this research to consider, from an economic perspective, the possibility that cancer patients may suffer a hindered quality of life, both during and after treatment, and may struggle to return to work. Another mathematical model further suggests early diagnosis and prompt treatment are crucial for achieving better cancer outcomes (Matos et al., 2021), which appears to be a common theme in the literature.

Overall, the forecasted delays in these two key cancer pathways in England highlight the daunting reality that a significant number of individuals in England are anticipated to encounter delayed diagnoses and treatment, resulting in worsened prognoses, preventable deaths and/or diminished quality of life. This analysis emphasises the urgent need for a re-evaluation of the post-COVID cancer recovery plan outlined by the NHS, with targets currently failing considerably to be met.

4.3. Has COVID-19 caused increased Late-stage Cancer diagnoses?

Cancer stage at diagnosis is a significant indicator of survival probability and prognosis of cancer patients (McPhail et al., 2015). Late-stage cancers (stages 3 and 4) are typically more challenging to treat and are associated with poorer prognoses for patients (Chakraborty and Rahman, 2019). As a result of delayed diagnoses and undiagnosed cases during the pandemic, this dissertation hypothesises a future increase in the proportion of late-stage diagnoses. This aligns with literature suggesting that the reduction in routine primary care referrals will inevitably translate into a higher rate of later-stage presentations (Watt, Sullivan and Aggarwal, 2022), and that the postponement of screening procedures is likely to cause a surge in advanced stage diagnoses “in the near-future” (Sessa et al., 2022).

To verify this hypothesis, visual methods are applied to the recent NHS data on Diagnoses by Stage.

Figure 8 depicts Monthly Total Diagnoses by Stage. As previously established, total diagnoses dropped significantly during the pandemic. Figure 8 depicts how this was also the case for all cancer stages. Analysing total diagnoses by stage may not capture important information on whether a higher percentage of patients are being diagnosed with late-stage cancers. A more informative approach is to analyse the proportion of diagnoses of each cancer stage as a share of total diagnoses, depicted in Figure 9.

Figure 9 shows that when the pandemic first hit, proportion of Stage 4 and ‘Unknown’ stage diagnoses increased. ‘Unknown’ stage is defined by CRUK as a case where “there isn’t enough information submitted about a person’s cancer when it gets recorded by the cancer registry to determine what stage it is” (Lowes, 2022). The pandemic saw a 17% increase in ‘Unknown’ cancers (Lowes, 2022), resulting in less knowledge regarding severity of diagnosed cancers. Whilst this complicates data analysis by making it difficult to draw conclusions about distributional changes in early/late-stage cancer diagnoses, two things are evident. Firstly, ‘Unknown’ diagnoses can only have

unwanted effects considering the time-dependent nature of many cancers (Neal et al., 2015). Ambiguity and indecisiveness regarding treatment will only hinder prognosis. Secondly, considering 'Unknown' cases constitute almost 35% of all cases in the most recent month, significantly higher than any of the other four stages, further research into these unknown cases is critical for maximally effective policymaking.

Overall, whilst the data analysis did not show a definitive uptick of the proportion of late-stage diagnoses, delays and growing backlogs in England are creating a breeding ground for cancer progression and later-stage diagnosis.

4.4. How did COVID-19 affect Cancer Treatment Inequality and the role of Telemedicine?

Recent literature has presented claims that the pandemic has widened cancer treatment inequalities. Those residing in poorer areas experienced greater reductions in the number of 2WW referrals during the pandemic (Watt, Sullivan and Aggarwal, 2022). Additionally, the elderly, who are at higher risk of COVID-19 complications, are likely to be the group most negatively impacted by foregone medical care during the pandemic (Zhang, 2021). This effect can be attributed to the risk of accessing regular healthcare being disproportionately higher for elderly patients who have higher rates of health problems than young patients and, as such, are disincentivised from entering areas where they could contract COVID-19 (Martins Van Jaarsveld, 2020). This phenomenon is particularly alarming in the context of cancer where over half of UK yearly cancer deaths are in individuals aged 75 and above (CRUK, 2015b). Consequently, those who compromised most on medical visits were also likely to be those most at risk of cancer morbidity and mortality.

The pandemic has catalysed the adoption of telemedicine and virtual healthcare. Remote appointments, which accounted for around 10% of UK general medical consultations prior to the pandemic, rose to 75% during its peak (McCall, 2020). This allowed patients who were fearful of entering high-risk COVID-19 settings to remain safe in their homes during medical consultations. A study conducted by Houston Methodist Hospital found that 92.6% of patients were satisfied with video-based medical visits and another survey found 82% would like to see telehealth services

maintained or expanded after the pandemic (West, Barzi and Wong, 2022). The implementation of telemedicine can mitigate geographical disparities in healthcare (Gajarawala and Pelkowski, 2020), increasing accessibility to specialised practitioners for patients in underserved areas and with physical limitations such as the elderly (West, Barzi and Wong, 2022).

A study examining adults aged 65 and over found that hearing or speaking problems, dementia, lack of internet-enabled hardware and limited use of electronic communication impeded their ability to engage with telemedicine. The analysis revealed the majority of over 65s were burdened by at least one of the above (West, Barzi and Wong, 2022). Similarly, a UK study found that some elderly patients struggled explaining conditions over the phone and might have lacked the skills or technology to upload photos or videos causing them to delay seeking care as a result (Coleman, 2021), which is particularly worrying as cancer risks increase exponentially with age (Estapé, 2018).

In summary, telehealth advancements during the pandemic can be regarded as a notable achievement, by helping to narrow health disparities based on socioeconomic status and strengthening the cancer pathway in the case of future emergencies (Witkowska-Zimny and Nieradko-Iwanicka, 2022). However, this dissertation acknowledges that it may exacerbate other health inequalities, particularly concerning age. Therefore, it is imperative to consider how COVID-19 has disproportionately affected cancer treatment in different demographics to guide effective policies and ensure equitable access to cancer treatment for all.

4.5. How did COVID-19 affect Cancer Trials?

The pandemic led to the suspension of many oncological trials (Sessa et al., 2022). A Phase 3 cancer trial costs on average \$20 million (Richards et al., 2020) translating to a direct and quantifiable financial cost when these trials are halted or restarted after being suspended. A study of 386 global oncological trials stopped between April 2020 and March 2021 found that 74 remained stopped (Sessa et al., 2022). Furthermore, CRUK reported that 95% of its UK cancer trials were halted during the pandemic (Research Professional News, 2020). In the short-term, patients already enrolled in

trials may suffer non-financial costs having been exposed to study drugs with potential adverse side-effects (Unger et al., 2016). Furthermore, patients desperate and willing to partake in new therapy trials miss an opportunity to reap the potential benefits of new treatments, with CRUK announcing that existing trial enrolment fell 87% during the pandemic in the UK (Research Professional News, 2020).

In the long-term, the financial burden of reactivating halted cancer trials means that other trials in the funding pipeline will be in jeopardy (Richards et al., 2020), resulting in potential breakthrough cancer treatments being denied approval. Clinical trials are considered the key step in advancing new treatments from research setting to a cancer treatment clinic (Unger et al., 2016). A study of 371,302 patient entries between 1997-2009 found a nearly 1:1 correlation between national oncological trial accrual rate and average percent change in the 5-year-survival rate (Unger et al., 2016) demonstrating the pivotal role of cancer trials in improving cancer outcomes.

Overall, limited funding for new trials, in conjunction with the substantial number of trials that were stopped globally and in England during the pandemic, will lead to a slowing in the technological progress of cancer treatments in the foreseeable future. This could have knock-on undesirable effects on cancer treatment success rates, morbidity, and mortality in England.

4.6. How does Cancer affect Employment?

To comprehensively examine the economic impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on cancer treatment, the effects of cancer on employment must be considered. A major UK survey of cancer survivors reported a highly statistically significant reduction in the percentage of survivors in full time-employment pre-diagnosis (53%) compared with post-diagnosis (33%). Additionally, average weekly working hours reduced from 38 hours to 32 hours (Luker et al., 2013). The study also suggests that early detection of cancer enables some people to work during treatment (Luker et al., 2013). Given this dissertation's forecast that significant future delays in 2WW will result in a greater proportion of late-stage diagnoses, which is also typically associated with greater physical pain (Cancer.org, 2018), it is expected that fewer people in England will be able to work during their treatment. Furthermore, a 2019 systematic review of English-

language studies found that chemotherapy, a treatment plan often employed on later-stage cases (CRUK, 2020), shared a significant negative association with work ability (Blinder and Gany, 2020). Thus, growing backlogs and delays in diagnosis and treatment are expected to reduce workforce productivity.

Chapter 5 – The OLG Model with Cancer

Following the framework developed in (Chakraborty, 2004), an OLG model is constructed and various ‘cancer-related’ parameters are introduced as a means to model the macroeconomic impact of the pandemic-induced changes in cancer services in England.

5.1. Model Specification

A two-period model is considered. At any time, young agents and old agents coexist in the economy. The young at time t become old at time $t+1$. Survival probability from the first period to the next, φ_t , is a function of the young agent’s health status at time t , h_t :

$$\varphi_t = \varphi(h_t), \quad (1)$$

where φ is a non-decreasing concave function.

A proportion of young agents, $1 - \varphi_t$, die at the end of period t . All remaining old die at the end of any given period. Everyone is born with a time endowment of 1 unit which is inelastically supplied to the labour market when young, earning a wage income, w_t . Health is assumed to be publicly provided and there is no private market for healthcare. An individual’s health status is entirely determined by the quality of the NHS and other public health measures, for example sanitation or vaccination programmes. Public health expenditure is financed through a proportional tax, $\tau_t \in (0,1)$ on wage - health investment per young person equals $\tau_t w_t$. A productivity parameter, $\gamma \in (0,1)$, is introduced, representing the level of technology of NHS treatments, or alternatively the productivity of the NHS’ health expenditure in improving individuals’ health status. As this model concerns cancer, γ denotes productivity of cancer treatments. Health status of the young is therefore characterised:

$$h_t = \gamma \tau_t w_t. \quad (2)$$

Generation- t individuals give birth to offspring before realising their mortality shock at the end of period t . Offspring only become economically active at time $t+1$. An individual cannot inherit their parents' health stock. Savings are introduced in the form of a perfect annuities market whereby all savings are intermediated through mutual funds. Young agents can either consume or save at time t . Capital is assumed the sole asset and the mutual fund invests savings on behalf of individuals, guaranteeing a gross rate of return, \hat{R}_{t+1} , for all surviving old. If young agents save and survive until old age, they can consume in the next period. Assuming the mutual fund earns a gross return R_{t+1} , perfect competition implies that in equilibrium, $\hat{R}_{t+1} = \frac{R_{t+1}}{\varphi_t}$.

Assuming logarithmic preferences, an individual maximises expected lifetime utility according to the function:

$$U_t = \ln[c_t^t] + \varphi_t \ln[c_{t+1}^t]. \quad (3)$$

Here, c denotes consumption, the subscript denotes in which period consumption is occurring and the superscript denotes in which period a decision is being made. This is to say that an individual only benefits from second period consumption with probability φ_t . Expected utility is maximised subject to the following budget constraints:

$$c_t^t \leq (1 - \tau_t)w_t - s_t, \quad (4)$$

$$c_{t+1}^t \leq \hat{R}_{t+1}s_t, \quad (5)$$

where s_t denotes savings and w_t and \hat{R}_{t+1} are assumed given. Equation (4) states that once a young agent has been taxed on their income and saved some of the remaining income, they cannot consume more than what remains. Equation (5) states that an old agent cannot consume more than the amount they saved multiplied by the guaranteed rate of return on their investment.

Individuals are assumed to be utility-maximising. The utility function is monotonically increasing with respect to consumption today and consumption tomorrow. Individuals will always benefit from exhausting their resources in both periods so the inequality

signs in the budget constraints are replaced with equality signs. At time t , young agents decide how much to consume and save to maximise expected lifetime utility. Optimal savings are found by assuming equality in (4) and (5) and solving the individual's optimal lifetime decision by substituting the resulting equations into (3), differentiating with respect to savings and setting equal to zero. This gives:

$$U_t = \ln[(1 - \tau_t)w_t - s_t] + \varphi_t \ln[\hat{R}_{t+1}s_t],$$

$$\frac{\partial U_t}{\partial s_t} = \frac{-1}{(1 - \tau_t)w_t - s_t} + \frac{\varphi_t}{s_t} = 0,$$

$$\rightarrow \frac{\varphi_t}{s_t} = \frac{1}{(1 - \tau_t)w_t - s_t},$$

$$\rightarrow s_t = \varphi_t(1 - \tau_t)w_t - \varphi_t s_t,$$

$$\rightarrow s_t = \frac{\varphi_t}{1 + \varphi_t} (1 - \tau_t)w_t,$$

$$\rightarrow s_t = \sigma_t(1 - \tau_t)w_t, \quad (6)$$

where $\sigma_t = \frac{\varphi_t}{1 + \varphi_t}$ is the savings propensity which is an increasing function of φ_t , the survival probability.

To find optimal consumption in period t , (6) is substituted into (4) (with equal sign as per above reasoning), yielding:

$$c_t^t = (1 - \sigma_t)(1 - \tau_t)w_t. \quad (7)$$

Next, total economy output takes the form of the Cobb-Douglas production function:

$$Y = F(K, L) = AK^\alpha L^{1-\alpha},$$

where Y denotes aggregate output, K is total capital, L is total labour, $\alpha \in (0,1)$ denotes share of total output attributed to capital and A is total factor productivity. Given the research task, exogenous changes in A are reduced to being specifically caused by changes in labour productivity. Output per worker is denoted:

$$y = \frac{Y}{L} = A \left(\frac{K}{L} \right)^\alpha = Ak^\alpha, \quad (8)$$

where $k = \frac{K}{L}$ denotes capital per worker.

Perfect competition is assumed in the final goods market implying both labour and capital earn their marginal products:

$$w_t = \frac{\partial Y}{\partial L} = (1 - \alpha)Ak_t^\alpha, \quad (9)$$

$$R_t = \frac{\partial Y}{\partial K} = \alpha Ak_t^{\alpha-1}. \quad (10)$$

5.2. Solving the General Equilibrium

Capital is assumed to fully depreciate from one period to the next. Thus, capital in the next period equals total savings today, which equals savings per worker multiplied by the size of the labour force:

$$K_{t+1} = s_t L_t. \quad (11)$$

Substituting young agents' optimal savings, (6), into (11) yields:

$$K_{t+1} = \sigma_t (1 - \tau_t) w_t L_t. \quad (12)$$

To investigate how the economy evolves over time, a fundamental equation governing the evolution of k_t , capital per worker, is sought. To this end:

$$\frac{K_{t+1}}{L_t} = \sigma_t(1 - \tau_t)w_t,$$

$$\rightarrow \frac{K_{t+1}}{L_{t+1}} \frac{L_{t+1}}{L_t} = \sigma_t(1 - \tau_t)w_t.$$

The term $\frac{L_{t+1}}{L_t}$ is replaced with $(1 + n)$, where n is the growth rate of the population.

The equation simplifies to the following:

$$k_{t+1} = \sigma_t \frac{(1 - \tau_t)}{(1 + n)} w_t. \quad (13)$$

Substituting (9) into (13) results in:

$$k_{t+1} = \sigma_t \frac{(1 - \tau_t)(1 - \alpha)}{(1 + n)} A k_t^\alpha, \quad (14)$$

where combining (1), (2) & (9) gives:

$$\sigma_t = \frac{\varphi_t}{1 + \varphi_t} = \frac{\varphi(h_t)}{1 + \varphi(h_t)} = \frac{\varphi(\gamma\tau_t w_t)}{1 + \varphi(\gamma\tau_t w_t)} = \frac{\varphi(\gamma\tau_t(1 - \alpha)A k_t^\alpha)}{1 + \varphi(\gamma\tau_t(1 - \alpha)A k_t^\alpha)}. \quad (15)$$

As φ is a non-decreasing function, equation (15) implies that savings propensity, σ_t , is increasing in γ , τ_t , $(1 - \alpha)$, A and k_t^α .

Equation (14) is the dynamic equilibrium equation governing the evolution of capital per worker over time. From this equation, information about the other parameters in the economy can be known.

5.3 – OLG Results

Equation (14) enables an understanding of the potential economic effects of the changes to cancer services discussed earlier in this dissertation. Chapter 4 supports the following three parametric effects:

1. Survival probability to next period, φ_t , directly decreases.
2. Productivity of cancer treatment, γ , decreases.
3. Productivity of labour, A , decreases.

Each of these are considered separately:

1. If survival probability (valued between 0 and 1) at time t , φ_t , decreases, then propensity to save, σ_t , decreases, as seen in (15). This is because, if an individual's expectation of surviving into the next period decreases, then they are more likely to consume now and save less for their increasingly uncertain future. From (14), this leads to reduced capital per worker in the next period because less is invested per worker into the mutual fund and thus into capital per worker in the next period. From (8), output per worker is increasing in capital per worker. Thus, output per worker also decreases in the next period.
2. A decrease in the productivity of cancer services in England, γ , will lead to a decrease in the survival probability, as seen in (15). With the same amount of funding (from taxed income), a decrease in the productivity of cancer treatments will result in higher cancer mortality. Thus, survival probability, φ_t , decreases. From here, the same argument as seen in 1. follows.
3. A decrease in the labour productivity parameter, A , has two effects on (14):

The direct effect is that lower labour productivity reduces the amount of output produced with a given level of input. This leads to a reduction in total output, as seen from the production function. As wage equals marginal product of labour, wages decrease. Assuming all else equal (in particular, taxes and

propensity to save), a reduction in wages leads to a reduction in savings per worker according to (6). Finally, capital in the next period is proportional to savings per worker according to (11). Thus, assuming no population growth, capital per worker decreases in the next period.

The indirect effect relies on survival probability being a function of labour productivity, A . Since a lower A implies lower wages, less income tax is collected for NHS cancer services expenditure, leading to a reduction in the survival probability from one period to the next. Thus, individuals are more likely to consume now rather than save for a more uncertain future, which results, *ceteris paribus*, in reduced capital per worker in the next period. This is because capital in the next period is an increasing function of savings per worker today.

An exogenous reduction in A therefore has two separate diminishing effects on capital per worker in the next period. From (8), output per worker consequently decreases in the next period.

According to the OLG model, all three parametric effects caused by the disruption to cancer services in England during the pandemic, lead to reduced capital per worker and output per worker in the next period.

Chapter 6 - Discussion & Informing Policy

This section uses the dissertation's research to guide policymakers on mitigating the adverse economic impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on cancer services in England.

6.1. Policies to Optimally Leverage the Utilisation of Telemedicine

Considering the NHS' Long-Term Plan to increase the prevalence of telemedicine appointments (Barrie, 2023), this dissertation devises strategies to optimally capitalise on this technology to enhance cancer service productivity in England.

Firstly, lower socio-economic regions in England have significantly lower cancer detection rates (Round et al., 2021) which may be attributed to disproportionately greater underfunding of these regions' GPs compared to their demand (Watt, Sullivan and Aggarwal, 2022). Decentralised healthcare that utilises online consultations can facilitate connections between poorer individuals and practitioners in other regions, thereby narrowing the funding imbalance across primary care and reducing cancer treatment inequalities arising from socioeconomic status. However, a Digital Exclusion Report found people in these regions are less likely to have access to digital equipment needed for online consultations (Coleman, 2021). Therefore, a scheme providing necessary digital equipment to those who need it is proposed, ensuring equitable access. This scheme could take the form of subsidy vouchers on essential equipment or the direct provision of equipment to primary care settings in underprivileged regions, with patients able to 'borrow' equipment as needed.

Furthermore, more than two fifths of NHS expenditure is on over 65s (Robineau, 2017). Therefore, paying particular attention to the delivery of telehealth to this cohort is vital. Section 4.4 highlights telemedicine's success for the elderly during the pandemic but also acknowledges its limitations, namely this age-group's lack of knowledge on basic telehealth technologies. To address this, the NHS should conduct educational sessions on using fundamental technologies necessary for efficient telehealth services. This initiative could lead to more productive online consultations while increasing the familiarity of elderly patients with utilising online services. This could alleviate resource constraints and reduce waiting times for patients whose in-person

consultations are deemed essential (Richards et al., 2020), increasing the productivity parameter, γ .

During the pandemic, cancer trials shifted towards decentralised approaches, namely greater utilisation of remote assessments and the shipping of investigational drugs to patients (Sessa et al., 2022). Whilst there still currently remains a need for in-person visits during trials (for example, for physical examination or blood tests etc.), these new approaches reduce costs associated with unnecessary in-person visits, enabling more patients to participate (Sessa et al., 2022). However, accrual of new patients decreased during the pandemic (Sessa et al., 2022), which is concerning given the compelling relationship between trial enrolments and improvements in cancer survival rates highlighted in Section 4.5. While telemedicine can help accelerate trial enrolment in the future, successful remote monitoring during trials necessitates appropriate technology and regulations allowing for private patient data to be used (Sessa et al., 2022). The first proposed policy involves providing financial support to those who lack the necessary telemedicine or offering financial incentives for trial participation, thereby increasing accruals. Secondly, international collaboration should be fostered to establish common standards regarding issues such as data protection, ensuring a worldwide, cooperative strive towards more successful cancer therapies. These strategies could offset the decrease in the treatment productivity parameter, γ , caused by the pandemic's dampening impact on cancer therapy innovations.

Finally, telemedicine can alleviate the underrepresentation of poorer patients and ethnic minorities in clinical trials in England (Sessa et al., 2022). The inequalities expressed above extend to trial participation as well, with patients from socioeconomically deprived areas of England only half as likely to be referred for a clinical trial compared with their more affluent counterparts (Guy's and St Thomas' NHS Foundation Trust, 2012). This may be attributed to barriers disproportionately impeding financially stricken patients, for example the time or travel expenses involved with traditional in-person visits and collecting investigational drugs (Sessa et al., 2022). Ensuring new treatment trials involve a representative sample of the population guarantees that trial results and successful new therapies can be effectively applied to all demographics (Guy's and St Thomas' NHS Foundation Trust, 2012). Therefore, the recommended policy involves providing financial support to those who cannot afford the necessary

telemedicine equipment for ‘virtual’ cancer trials, as well educating patients from underrepresented areas about the benefits of participating in these trials. These strategies would encourage equitable representation in cancer trials, allowing everyone to benefit from innovative new therapies, further increasing the treatment productivity parameter, γ , thereby acting to mitigate the pandemic-induced reduction of this parameter.

6.2. Support for Cancer Survivors

According to the model, another way to mitigate the adverse economic impact of the pandemic on cancer services is by counteracting the expected reduction in the labour productivity parameter, A .

A major study of UK cancer survivors revealed that patients who did not discuss employment issues with their treatment team were expected to work an average of 29.4h per week post-treatment, significantly lower than the average of 36.7h for those who engaged in such discussions (Luker et al., 2013).

Notably, over half of respondents did not discuss employment issues with their treatment team (Luker et al., 2013), consistent with other research suggesting that health professionals may be reluctant to initiate discussions on employment issues with patients (Peuckmann et al., 2009).

The reluctance of doctors to initiate such discussions, combined with the significant increase in post-treatment weekly hours worked amongst individuals who entered these discussions with their treatment team, emphasises the importance of implementing consultation-based schemes focused solely on advising, and harnessing, cancer survivors’ return to work. Importantly, these consultations should be conducted by professionals who are appropriately trained in addressing the employment-related concerns of cancer survivors. Such schemes should be offered and actively promoted by the NHS.

By doing so, the loss of productivity associated with the underutilisation of the skills and expertise of cancer survivors could be mitigated by facilitating their successful

reintegration into the workforce. This, in turn, would counteract the reduction in labour productivity, A , caused by the pandemic and would act to increase capital per worker and output per worker in the next period according to equations (14) and (8) from the OLG model, respectively.

7. Conclusion

The objective of this research was to gain deeper insight into how the pandemic has truly affected NHS cancer services in England and to consequently inform policymakers on potential strategies to offset these effects.

It is inevitable that NHS cancer services will be severely strained in the foreseeable future. A backlog of undiagnosed cancers, coupled with profound downward projections of key NHS cancer pathways and the halting of potentially breakthrough cancer trials, together converge to themes of delayed and later-stage diagnoses, excess mortality and morbidity, and reduced productivity of cancer treatments in England. Labour productivity amongst cancer patients, both during and post-treatment, is also expected to decrease with the predicted influx of more severe cancers. This dissertation's OLG model reported that these factors can negatively impact the future macroeconomic landscape and points towards a grave situation which demands immediate attention.

This report establishes a comprehensive and timely set of recommendations for the mitigation of these undesirable economic effects. These include policies on how to smoothly channel proven new cancer therapies into the NHS at scale and pace, how to optimally leverage telemedicine to accelerate cancer trial enrolments and reduce England's pre-existing cancer treatment inequalities, enabling equitable cancer treatment accessibility for all, and finally how to facilitate the reintegration of cancer survivors into the workforce. This dissertation believes that, without the implementation of such recommendations set out in this report, England and the NHS are heading towards a multi-dimensional cancer crisis, which will adversely affect the economy.

The generalisability of this research is subject to several factors. Although most findings are cancer-specific, other chronic diseases such as diabetes, pulmonary diseases, and hypertension, experienced similar delays during the pandemic (Chudasama et al., 2020). The simplicity of the OLG model enables its applicability to other diseases, with only slight adjustments to parameters necessary, but only in countries with a similar, predominantly public healthcare system. This model would

not, in its current form, extend to countries like the USA, where only private healthcare exists.

Further research is recommended to develop an economic model that can incorporate the complexities of cancer, incorporating the notion that different types of cancers have varying impacts on different demographics, thereby overcoming the simplicity of the OLG model introduced in this dissertation. Future models should also aim to eradicate the unlikely assumption that an individual's health status is solely determined by factors beyond their control and should instead consider the role of personal responsibility in shaping health status. By developing more nuanced models reflecting the complexity of cancer and incorporating more realistic assumptions, it will be possible to gain a more accurate understanding of cancer's economic impact and enable policymakers to devise better-informed, targeted, and more effective strategies in the future to mitigate these economic impacts.

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